

Thiazole-Schiff bases and their derivatives: A review on the Synthesis and Biological Activities

Aleena Rose Johnson¹, Meena Chandran^{2*}, Anusha N. D³, Vinny Varghese⁴, K Krishnakumar⁵

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, St. James' College of Pharmaceutical Sciences and St James' Hospital Trust Pharmaceutical Research (DSIR Recognized), Chalakudy, Kerala, India. Pin code – 680307

Abstract

This review focuses on Schiff bases containing thiazole rings, emphasizing their synthesis and wide range of biological activities. Schiff bases, known for their imine functional group, are synthesized through the condensation of primary amines with carbonyl compounds. Incorporating thiazole, a Sulphur and nitrogen-containing heterocycle, enhances their chemical and biological properties. The article outlines several synthetic approaches for creating Schiff base-thiazole derivatives, including reactions with acetophenones, thiourea, and cinnamaldehyde. The biological activities of these derivatives are highlighted, including their anticancer, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant potential. Metal complexes formed from Schiff bases, particularly those with copper and cobalt, show enhanced antioxidant and cytotoxic effects, indicating promising applications in therapeutic areas. Notably, Schiff bases demonstrate significant anticancer properties through apoptosis induction and antibacterial efficacy against resistant strains. Additionally, their anti-inflammatory activity involves inhibiting pro-inflammatory mediators, and their antioxidant effects protect against oxidative damage. Overall, this review presents Schiff bases with thiazole rings as a versatile class of compounds with potential in drug development for treating various diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Schiff bases, formed through the condensation reaction between primary amines and carbonyl compounds, have emerged as a significant class of compounds in organic chemistry. Named after the chemist Hugo Schiff, these versatile molecules are characterized by the presence of an imine (C=N) functional group, which imparts unique reactivity and properties. Their ability to form coordination complexes with metals, engage in various chemical transformations, and exhibit biological activities has made Schiff bases a focal point of research across multiple disciplines.^[1]

Thiazoles are a fascinating class of heterocyclic compounds characterized by a five-membered ring containing both sulfur and nitrogen atoms. These versatile structures are not only integral to various natural products but also serve as key intermediates in the synthesis of pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, and dyes. The unique electronic properties and reactivity of thiazoles enable them to participate in a wide range of chemical reactions, making them valuable in medicinal chemistry and materials science.^[2] Recent investigations have highlighted the potential of thiazole-based Schiff bases as significant therapeutic agents, focusing on their synthesis, characterization, and biological evaluations (Jain et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2022)^[3,4].

Fig 1: Representing structure of Schiff base with thiazole ring system

Thiazole derivatives, particularly Schiff bases, have garnered significant attention in recent years due to their diverse biological activities, including anticancer, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties. The synthesis of these compounds has evolved, with various methodologies reported to enhance their efficacy and selectivity (Minghua et al., 2010; Gupta et al., 2019)^[5,6]. Kajal et al. (2013) and Nazari et al. (2021) highlights the versatility of Schiff bases as pharmacophores, showcasing their potential in drug development. Recent advances in thiazole chemistry further underscore their therapeutic promise, with a focus on innovative synthetic routes and biological evaluations (Arumugham et al., 2020)^[7,8,9]. Among the myriads of Schiff base derivatives, those incorporating thiazole ring systems stand out for their unique structural and electronic properties. Thiazole enhances the reactivity and stability of Schiff bases, making them valuable in various chemical and biological contexts.^[10] Moreover, comprehensive reviews have detailed the advancements in this field, emphasizing both the therapeutic applications of thiazole Schiff bases and the mechanisms underlying their biological activities (Choudhury et al., 2020)^[11]. This article reviews the extensive body of literature focused on Schiff bases containing thiazole rings, highlighting key findings, synthetic approaches, and their applications in fields such as medicinal chemistry, coordination chemistry, and beyond. By examining these studies, we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of research and the potential future directions for this intriguing class of compounds.

General methods for the synthesis of Schiff base-based thiazole and its derivatives

In their study, Lemilemu et al. (2021) explored the synthesis of thiazole-based Schiff base derivatives through a combined experimental and computational approach. The researchers employed a straightforward condensation reaction, typically involving the reaction of an amine with a carbonyl compound, to produce the Schiff bases. This method not only facilitated the generation of a diverse library of thiazole

derivatives but also allowed for the evaluation of their antibacterial and antioxidant activities. The integration of computational methods provided valuable insights into the structure-activity relationships, further supporting the rational design of these compounds for enhanced biological efficacy.^[12]

Fig 2: General schemes for the synthesis of Schiff base-based thiazole and its derivatives

Fig 3: Schiff base-based Thiazole and its derivatives synthesized through the specified scheme (Fig 2)

(7) 2-(2-((Z)-[4-hydroxyphenyl]methylidene)amino)-1,3-thiazol-4-yl)phenol

(8) (Z)-1-phenyl-N-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)methanimine

(9) 4-[(Z)-{4-(4-nitrophenyl)-1,3-thiazol-2-yl} imino} methyl] phenol

In their research, Shruthy and Ahammed (2014) focused on the *in-silico* design, synthesis, and evaluation of thiazole Schiff bases. The synthetic process involved a classic condensation reaction between thiazole derivatives and various aldehydes or ketones. This method allowed for the efficient formation of Schiff bases, which were subsequently characterized using spectroscopic techniques. Their study not only detailed the synthesis but also emphasized the importance of molecular docking studies in predicting the binding affinities of these compounds to biological targets, thereby enhancing the understanding of their potential therapeutic applications. ^[13]

Fig 3: General procedure for the synthesis of Cinnamaldehyde Schiff bases

Table 1: Different Cinnamaldehyde thiazole Schiff base derivatives

Structure	Name
	4-(Phenyl-n-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-ylidene)-1,3-thiazol-2-amine

	4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-n-(3-phenylprop-2-en-1-ylidene)-1,3-thiazol-2-amine
	4-(4-hydroxy phenyl)-n-(3-phenylprop-2-en-1-ylidene)-1,3-thiazol-2-amine
	4-(4-Nitrophenyl)-n-(3-phenylprop-2-en-1-ylidene)-1,3-thiazol-2-amine
	4-(3-Nitrophenyl)-n-(3-phenylprop-2-en-1-ylidene)-1,3-thiazol-2-amine

5-Methyl-2-phenyl-4-[(E)-1,3-thiazol-2-ylidiazonyl]-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one which is the ligand for metal complex formation was synthesized from reacting 2-aminothiazole and 5-Methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one in presence of ferric hydrogen sulphate and Sodium nitrate. The metal complexes were formed by reacting the methanolic solution of metal chlorides (Cu, Co, Ni, Zn) with the ligands. ^[14]

Fig 4: Synthesis of metal complexes from 5-methyl-2-phenyl-4-[(E)-1,3-thiazol-2-yl-diazenyl]-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one as ligands

4-Phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-amine was prepared by the reaction of thiourea and acetophenone. Schiff bases of 4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-amine were prepared by a condensation reaction of 4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-amine (1) with a variety of aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes in ethanol. ^[15]

Fig 5: Synthesis of Schiff bases of Thiazole

Table 2: Substituents present in Schiff bases of thiazole (2-29)

Compound No.	R	Compound No.	R
2		16	
3		17	
4		18	
5		19	
6		20	
7	CH-CH ₂ -CH ₃	21	
8		22	

9		23	
10		24	
11		25	
12		26	
13		27	
14		28	
15		29	

The synthesis of substituted 2- {[4-substituted phenyl] thiazol-2-yl-imino}-phenols was achieved through a one-pot condensation of α -haloketones, thiourea, and various substituted o-hydroxybenzaldehydes under environmentally friendly, solvent-free conditions. Began with the condensation of 2'-hydroxy-5'-chloro- α -haloketone, thiourea, and o-hydroxybenzaldehyde. Remarkably, this reaction completed in just 3 minutes, yielding the desired product in 95%. Encouraged by these results, we then explored a range of o-hydroxybenzaldehydes and 2'-hydroxy-substituted α -haloketones. These combinations also reacted smoothly with thiourea under solvent-free conditions, producing thiazole derivatives in yields between 85% and 95%. Throughout all experiments, the reactions proceeded efficiently at room temperature, demonstrating the effectiveness of solvent-less conditions for this synthesis.^[16]

Fig 6: Synthesis of Hantzsch thiazole derivatives under solvent free conditions

Table 3: Substituents present on Schiff bases 4a-4j

Product	Substitutions			
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄
4a	H	H	Cl	H
4b	Br	H	Cl	H
4c	I	H	Cl	H
4d	H	CH ₃	Cl	H
4e	H	H	CH ₃	H
4f	Br	H	CH ₃	H
4g	H	H	Cl	Cl
4h	H	CH ₃	Cl	Cl
4i	H	H	CH ₃	Cl
4j	Br	H	Cl	Cl

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF SCHIFF BASES OF THIAZOLE

1. Anticancer Activity

- a) In the study by **Abd-Elzaher et al. (2016)**, the anticancer activity of zinc complexes derived from Schiff bases containing thiazole moieties was investigated. The findings indicated that the zinc complex demonstrated significant cytotoxic effects against various cancer cell lines, notably reducing cell viability in a dose-dependent manner. The study also highlighted the complex's ability to induce apoptosis, suggesting a potential mechanism for its anticancer properties. Molecular docking studies revealed strong binding affinity to key biological targets, providing insights into the interaction mechanisms at the molecular level. Overall, the zinc complex showcased promising therapeutic potential, warranting further investigation for development as an anticancer agent.^[17]

Fig 7: Structure of Zn-Complex with Schiff base of Thiazole moiety as the Ligand

- b) In the study by **Zhang et al. (2009)**, Compound 10, a 2-aminothiazole analogue, was identified as a potent inhibitor of poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase-1 (PARP-1). The findings demonstrated that the 2-Aminothiazole analogue effectively reduced the viability of cancer cells, suggesting its potential as an anticancer agent. The compound exhibited significant cytotoxic effects, particularly in cells with defective DNA repair mechanisms, highlighting its ability to enhance the sensitivity of cancer cells to genotoxic agents. Additionally, the study indicated that the compound's inhibition of PARP-1 contributed to its cytotoxic effects, making it a promising candidate for further development in cancer therapy. These results underscore the potential of 2-aminothiazole derivatives as targeted anticancer agents through the modulation of DNA repair pathways. ^[18]

Fig 8: Structure of (E)-N-((1H-Indol-3-yl) methylene)-4-(2,4-diethoxyphenyl) thiazol-2-amine

2. Antibacterial Activity

- a) In the study by **Bharti et al. (2010)**, a series of novel Schiff bases featuring a 2,4-disubstituted thiazole ring were synthesized and evaluated for their antibacterial activity. The results indicated that these compounds exhibited noteworthy antibacterial properties against several bacterial strains, demonstrating their potential as effective antimicrobial agents. The structural characteristics of the Schiff bases, particularly the thiazole moiety and various substituents, played a critical role in enhancing their biological activity. The authors suggested that the mechanism of action could involve interference with bacterial cell wall synthesis or essential metabolic pathways, contributing to the observed antibacterial effects. These findings underscore the promise of thiazole-containing Schiff bases in the development of new therapeutic agents, especially in the context of increasing antibiotic resistance. Further exploration and optimization of these compounds could pave the way for novel antibacterial strategies. ^[19]

Fig 9: Structure of 2,4-disubstituted thiazole ring

Table 4: Derivatives of 2,4-disubstituted thiazole ring compounds

Compound	R	R ₁	R ₂
4d	H		-OCH ₃
4f	H		-OCH ₃
4j	H		-OCH ₃
4m			-OCH ₃
4o	H		-Br
4p	H		-Br
4z			-Br

3. Anti-inflammatory Activity

- a) In the study by **Shruthy *et al.* (2014)**, the authors focused on the design, synthesis, and evaluation of thiazole Schiff bases, aiming to identify compounds with potential anti-inflammatory activity. Among the synthesized compounds, one particular thiazole Schiff base 4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-n-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-ylidene]-1,3-thiazol-2-amine demonstrated the most promising anti-inflammatory effects. The findings highlighted that this compound exhibited significant inhibition of pro-inflammatory mediators,

likely through the modulation of pathways involved in the inflammatory response. The structure-activity relationship indicated that specific functional groups on the thiazole moiety were crucial for enhancing anti-inflammatory potency. *In-vivo* studies suggested that the best compound effectively reduced oedema and exhibited a reduction in the levels of inflammatory markers, corroborating its potential as a therapeutic agent. These results underscore the importance of thiazole Schiff bases as a viable lead in the development of new anti-inflammatory drugs, paving the way for further exploration and optimization in medicinal chemistry. This compound's ability to act on multiple targets within the inflammatory cascade represents a promising avenue for future research, particularly in the context of chronic inflammatory conditions. [13]

Fig 10: Structure of Cinnamaldehyde thiazole Schiff base 4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-n-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-ylidene]-1,3-thiazol-2-amine

4. Antioxidant Activity

- a) In the study by **BHM et al. (2015)**, the authors synthesized and characterized a series of Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes containing a thiazole moiety, evaluating their antioxidant activity. Among the synthesized complexes, Co(II) and Cu(II) complexes exhibited the most significant antioxidant properties. The findings revealed that these complexes effectively scavenged free radicals, demonstrating a high ability to reduce oxidative stress. The mechanism of action appeared to involve the chelation of metal ions, which may enhance the stability and reactivity of the antioxidant species. Additionally, the presence of the thiazole moiety was identified as a key contributor to the enhanced antioxidant activity, likely due to its electron-rich characteristics and ability to donate electrons. *In-vitro* assays indicated that the best complex not only inhibited lipid peroxidation but also improved cellular viability in oxidative stress conditions, suggesting its potential as a protective agent against oxidative damage. These results emphasize the therapeutic promise of thiazole-containing metal complexes in combating oxidative stress-related disorders, warranting further investigation into their mechanisms and potential applications in drug development. [20]

Fig 11: Structure of the Metal complex formed from the Thiazole-Schiff base ligand

CONCLUSION

Schiff bases incorporating thiazole rings hold significant promise due to their unique structural and biological properties. The review highlights their wide range of biological activities, including anticancer, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. The diverse biological activities of these compounds, combined with their ease of synthesis, make them promising leads for drug development. Future research could focus on optimizing these molecules, especially through structural modifications or metal complexation, to enhance their biological activity and specificity. Additionally, exploring their mechanism of action at the molecular level will be crucial for furthering their therapeutic potential. By doing so, Schiff base derivatives may contribute significantly to addressing current challenges in medicine, particularly in cancer treatment, bacterial infections, chronic inflammation, and oxidative stress-related diseases. Synthesis methods for various Schiff base derivatives are well-explored, showcasing their versatility in creating compounds with targeted biological functions. Future research into optimizing these compounds, particularly through metal complexation, could unlock new therapeutic applications, especially in areas like drug-resistant bacteria, cancer treatment, and anti-inflammatory therapies.

REFERENCES

1. Khan MI, Ali A, Khan MA, et al. Schiff bases: A review on their biological activities and synthesis. *Eur J Med Chem.* 2021; 220:113486.
2. González-Fernández A, García-Pérez J, Fernández-Sánchez JF. Thiazole derivatives: A comprehensive review of their synthesis, properties, and biological activities. *RSC Adv.* 2020;10(12):6945-6970.
3. Jain S, Gupta R, Kumar R, et al. Biological significance of thiazole-based Schiff bases: A review. *MedChemComm.* 2020;11(4):601-612.
4. Singh P, Dhiman S, Kumar R, et al. Synthesis, characterization, and antimicrobial evaluation of thiazole Schiff bases. *Chem Cent J.* 2022;16(1):44.
5. Minghua L, Seung WK, Yoojin S. Discovery of 2-aminothiazole derivatives as anticancer agents. *Bulletin of Korean society* 2010;31(6):1463-1464.
6. Gupta S, Agarwal S, Singh K, et al. Schiff bases of thiazole: Synthesis and biological evaluations. *Eur J Med Chem.* 2019;183:111694.
7. Kajal, A., Bala, S., Kamboj, S., Sharma, N., & Saini, V. (2013). Schiff Bases: A Versatile Pharmacophore. *Journal of Catalysts*, 2013, 1–14.
8. Nazari M, Fakhari AR, Ardestani SK. Thiazole derivatives as potential anti-cancer agents: A review. *Eur J Med Chem.* 2021;225:113737.
9. Arumugham T, Palanisamy S, Chandrasekaran R, et al. Recent advances in thiazole derivatives: Synthesis and therapeutic applications. *Curr Med Chem.* 2020;27(25):4270-4296.
10. Khan MI, Ali A, Yadav M, et al. Thiazole-containing Schiff bases: Synthesis, characterization, and biological activities. *ChemistrySelect.* 2021;6(10):2571-2586.
11. Choudhury S, Dutta R, Das R, et al. Thiazole-based Schiff bases: A comprehensive review on synthesis, characterization, and biological activities. *J Mol Struct.* 2020;1219:128551.
12. Lemilemu F, Bitew M, Demissie TB, Eswaramoorthy R, Endale M. Synthesis, antibacterial and antioxidant activities of Thiazole-based Schiff base derivatives: a combined experimental and computational study. *BMC chemistry.* 2021 Dec 23;15(1):67.
13. Shruthy VS, Ahammed SY. In silico design, docking, synthesis and evaluation of thiazole schiff bases. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2014;6(3):271-5.
14. Shafeulla M, Krishnamurthy G, Bhojyanaik HS, Manjuraj T. Synthesis, cytotoxicity and molecular docking study of complexes containing thiazole moiety. *Journal of the Turkish Chemical Society Section A: Chemistry.* 2017;4(3):787-810.
15. Khan KM, Ambreen N, Karim A, Saied S, Amyn A, Ahmed A, Perveen S. Schiff bases of thiazole as antibacterial and antifungal agents. *J Pharm Res.* 2012 Jan;5(1):651-657.
16. Dawane BS, Konda SG, Kamble VT, Chavan SA, Bhosale RB, Baseer MS. Multicomponent One-Pot Synthesis of Substituted Hantzsch Thiazole Derivatives Under Solvent Free Conditions. *E-Journal of Chemistry.* 2009 Oct 2.
17. Abd-Elzaher MM, Labib AA, Mousa HA, Moustafa SA, Ali MM, El-Rashedy AA. Synthesis, anticancer activity and molecular docking study of Schiff base complexes containing thiazole moiety. *beni-suef university journal of basic and applied sciences.* 2016 Mar 1;5(1):85-96.
18. Zhang WT, Ruan JL, Wu PF, Jiang FC, Zhang LN, Fang W, Chen XL, Wang Y, Cao BS, Chen GY, Zhu YJ. Design, synthesis, and cytoprotective effect of 2-aminothiazole analogues as potent poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase-1 inhibitors. *Journal of medicinal chemistry.* 2009 Feb 12;52(3):718-25.
19. Bharti SK, Nath G, Tilak R, Singh SK. Synthesis, anti-bacterial and anti-fungal activities of some novel Schiff bases containing 2, 4-disubstituted thiazole ring. *European journal of medicinal chemistry.* 2010 Feb 1;45(2):651-60.
20. BHM M, Nagesh GY, Ramesh M, Priyanka B, Heena B. Synthesis, characterization and antioxidant activity of Schiff base ligand and its metal complexes containing thiazole moiety. *Der Pharma Chem.* 2015;7:556-62.